

ENGINEERING THE DAMPING PROPERTIES OF MULTILAYER THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Thermoplastic composites consisting of a micro/nano-composite matrix reinforced with woven glass fibres were developed. Different filler compositions were used with the aim of designing the viscoelastic properties of the composites, characterized by layers of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics and micro/nano reinforced PP matrices.

Keywords: Nanocomposites; Thermoplastic Composite; Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

The use of inorganic fillers is a common practice in the plastics industry to improve some properties of thermoplastics, such as heat distortion temperature, hardness, toughness and stiffness. The effects of filler on the mechanical and other properties depend strongly on its nature, shape, particle size, aggregate size, surface characteristics and degree of dispersion in the polymer. In recent years, intensive research efforts have been devoted to the development of nanocomposites to achieve improved performances even at low content of nanofillers. In general, the mechanical properties of particulate composites filled with micron-sized filler particles are lower than those filled with nanoparticles of the same filler content [1,2]. The properties of ternary systems with nano- and micro- fillers in polypropylene matrices have been recently studied in our group [3].

The mechanical properties of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics are affected by the interfacial adhesion between the glass fibre and the polymeric matrix, the length and the diameter of the fibre, the fibre volume fraction, the fibre orientation, and their distribution in the composite [4]. Coupling agents are usually used to improve the adhesion between the fibres and the polymeric matrix [5].

The nano/micro particles dispersed in the thermoplastic matrix have the potential to improve the matrix-dominated properties in continuous fibre reinforced composite and in particular by improving the compressive and flexural strength of the fibre composites. The compressive strength of continuous fibre composites is usually lower than the tensile strength, because the fibres can easily buckle under a compressive load. The compressive strength depends on the modulus of the matrix [6–8], because a higher modulus increases the lateral support of the fibres and, therefore, reduces the tendency for fibre micro buckling or kinking.

Thermoplastic composites consisting of a micro/nano-composite matrix reinforced with woven glass fibres were therefore developed. Different filler compositions were used with the aim of designing the structural and viscoelastic properties of the composites, characterized by layers of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics and micro/nano reinforced PP matrices. The effects of matrix composition, polymeric film thickness and processing conditions on viscoelastic and mechanical properties of the final multilayered thermoplastic composites are discussed in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Polypropylene (Moplen HP500J), supplied by Basel Polyolefins, was used as polymeric matrix. Polypropylene *grafted* maleic anhydride (Polybond 3200, containing 1 wt% of maleic anhydride), supplied by Crompton, was used as compatibilizer. The organoclay used is Nanofil 5, supplied by Sud-Chemie. The calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), with a density of 2,93 g/ml, was purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Glass fiber fabrics were used as reinforcements in composites preparation; the woven fabric was supplied by Teximpianti S.p.a., with a thickness of 0.22 mm and a weight of 290 g/m².

Preparation

All the components were dried at 100 °C for 18h before processing. The mixing process was carried out in a Haake Rheomix 600 internal mixer. The mixing temperature was set to 170 °C and the rotor speed was 70 rpm. The nano- and nano/micro-composites were prepared by melt blending the PP, PPgMA and nanoclays for 3 min, after that CaCO_3 microparticles were added in the mixing chamber, when applicable. The total mixing time in every case was 10 min. These materials were then used to prepare thin films by compression moulding.

Composite were than prepared by alternating layers of matrix material films and woven fibre reinforcement. The films and fibre fabric were stacked in a closed mould and heated for 3 min at 200°C under a pressure of 3 bars and then was impregnated at the same temperature under a pressure of 15 bars for 15 min. The composite plate was cooled under the same pressure at a rate of approximately 8 °C/min.

Testing

The effect of composition on mechanical properties was carried out on a mechanical dynamometer (Instron 4204) at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min.

The storage and loss modulus of the samples were determined with Dynamical Mechanical Analysis (DMA). The samples were tested in a Triton DMA at a temperature range from -20 to 140 °C, heating rate 4°C/min, single cantilever mode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Properties of the nano/micro composite matrices

The tensile modulus of nano-/micro-composites and micro-composites containing the same wt% of inorganic filler are presented in figure 1. The composites containing only calcium carbonate have a Young's modulus approximately from 20% to 30% lower than the nano- /micro-composites containing the same total amount of inorganic components.

Figure 1. Young modulus comparison between nano/micro- and micro-composites containing the same wt% of inorganic filler [3]

Glass fiber composite with nano-/micro reinforced polymeric matrix

Figure 2 show two different magnifications of the composite prepared with a matrix containing 40% of micro particles (sample *CE_40_04*). From these micrographs we can observe, in a qualitative way, the degree of fibre impregnation and evaluate, quantitatively, the variation of thickness of the particulate reinforced matrix interlayers. Table 2 summarizes these data for all the composites investigated

Table 1 Thickness of interlayers

sample	v_p [wt%]	t_{0m} [mm]	t_{fm} [mm]	t_{fc} [mm]	v_f [wt%]
CE_30_03	30 micro	0,3	0,16	1,35	35
CE_40_03	40 micro	0,3	0,20	1,40	35
CE_40_04	40 micro	0,4	0,30	1,47	32
CE_40_05	40 micro	0,5	0,40	1,75	30
CE_50_03	50 micro	0,3	0,26	1,41	35
CE_NM_03	7(nano)+15(micro)	0,3	0,12	1,20	35

where v_p e v_f are respectively the weight fraction of particulate fillers (CaCO_3 and organoclays) and fiber reinforcement, while t_{0m} and t_{fm} are the matrix thickness before and after the film stacking process. Finally t_{fc} is the thickness of composite samples.

First, the final thickness of the interlayers t_{fm} is always lower than the initial thickness t_{0m} , suggesting that part of the polymer in the film is penetrated into the interstices of the fibres within the fabric. The reduction of thickness (both t_{fm} and t_{fc}) after the compression molding was found to be dependent by the concentration of micro and nano-particles initially present in the thermoplastic films employed for the film stacking process.

Figure 2 Micrographs of the sample CE_40_04 at two different magnifications(5x e 10x)

The penetration of polymer from the film to the interstices of the fibers within the fabric is good even when the concentration of micro-particle is high (30% and 40%) or when the nano- and micro-particles are used together. Due to the flow of the polymeric matrix within the fabric, the filler concentration in the interlayers is therefore higher than the initial value. The final multilayered composite structure is most likely characterized by alternating layers of a) fabric reinforced laminas based on nanoreinforced matrices and b) micro-sized rich particulate composites.

Figure 3 Storage modulus G' of multilayer thermoplastic composites

The storage modulus G' versus temperature of composite samples containing different amount of micro particles is reported in Figure 3. In spite of what expected, the storage

modulus of the particulate composites did not increase with the increase of filler concentration. In particular, we observed a reduction of the storage modulus when the amount of micro-particles increased from 30% to 40%. The increase of modulus was observed, instead, when the amount of filler raised from 40% to 50%. The motivation of this behaviour can be ascribed to the different thicknesses of the interlayers which developed after the compression moulding of the samples (see table 1).

However, it is interesting to observe that the storage modulus of composites containing both micro and nano particles was more than 300% higher than the other composites based only on micro fillers. The interlayer thickness t_{fm} of samples CE_NM_03 (0.12 mm) is 25% lower than the thickness of samples CE_30_03 (0.16 mm) and alone does not justify this remarkable increase in G' . Therefore, together with the lower interlayer thickness, the higher elastic modulus of the nanocomposite phase (see Figure 1) and the good impregnation have contributed to the higher performance of these thermoplastic composites based on nanocomposite matrix.

The effect of initial thickness of the polymeric films (0.3mm, 0.4mm, 0.5mm) on the dynamic-mechanical properties of the thermoplastic composites was evaluated. As expected, the increase of the film thickness, which resulted in interlayers with higher thickness (respectively 0.2mm, 0.3mm, 0.4mm) led to composite with lower storage modulus and with higher loss factor (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Loss factor of composites prepared with films having different initial thickness

Therefore, the possibility of modulating a) the final thickness of the interlayers and b) the content of both micro- and nano- fillers can allow the design of materials with different mechanical and damping properties.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermoplastic composites consisting of a reinforcing phase of glass fabrics in micro and micro/nano-composite matrices were prepared by using the film stacking technology. Different filler compositions were used to modify the rheological and mechanical properties of the polymeric matrix. In particular micro and micro/nano-composites

improved the matrix dominated flexural properties of continuous fibre reinforced composites by means of increasing the matrix modulus.

The penetration of the polymer from the film to the interstices of the fibers within the fabric was good even when the concentration of micro-particles was high. The best mechanical performances were obtained when nano and micro sized particles were combined to reinforce the thermoplastic matrices used for the films stacking technique. However, depending on the filler concentration and initial thickness of the films, it was possible to design materials with tailored rigidity and damping properties.

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